

Review report on extended abstract titled “Open Humanities Manifesto – an advocacy case for humanities in the Open Science era”

Authors (alphabetically by last name)

Serafeim Chatzopoulos^a (0000-0003-1714-5225), Angelo di Iorio^b (0000-0002-6893-7452)

^aATHENA RC, Greece; ^bUniversity of Bologna, Italy

Feedback Reviewer 1 Serafeim Chatzopoulos

Reviewer 1					
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID5	5	4	3	4	Accept

This submission highlights the importance of aligning research assessment practices with the principles of open science, with a particular focus on the humanities. It emphasises on advocacy by proposing concrete policy recommendations that add practical value. To strengthen the contribution, the authors might consider elaborating on how the OHM can be implemented in different institutional contexts, providing relevant examples. Overall, it is a relevant and well-aligned addition to the program of the conference.

Feedback Reviewer 2 Angelo di Iorio

Reviewer 2					
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID5	5	4	2	3	Accept

The abstract is clear and the project looks interesting. I think it can foster fruitful discussion at the conference. The proposed ideas are actually not new and, more than the novelty of the proposal itself, I think what is valuable is the discussion about the practical issues in implementing such an approach in a national context. The comparison and exchanges with similar projects in other countries is a key factor in my opinion. Indeed I would suggest authors strengthen the analysis of similar projects and manifestos in the final poster, and also focus on how to join this effort with other ones.